

ON THE INTERACTION BETWEEN NONLINEAR SOLITARY WAVES AND LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Experiments and numerical calculations are performed to study the interaction between nonlinear solitary waves in granular chains and laminated composite beams made of carbon fibre/epoxy (CFRP) or glass fibre/epoxy (GFRP) composites. The experiments were conducted using a vertical array of 21 steel beads contacting a simply-supported composite beam at mid-span. A striker bead was dropped from a given height to initiate the propagation of a single solitary wave in the granular chain, whose interaction with the beam gave rise to the propagation of multiple reflected solitary waves. The developed apparatus allowed measuring the delays and amplitudes of the reflected solitary waves, and the obtained measurements were found in good agreement with numerical predictions based on discrete elements and classical beam theory. It was found that the delay and amplitude ratios of the reflected solitary waves are highly sensitive to the lamina properties, composite layup and thickness of the tested laminate, concluding that the developed apparatus is capable of measuring directional stiffness variations in engineering composites, offering a low-cost and time-efficient alternative to conventional destructive test protocols.

1 INTRODUCTION

The propagation of nonlinear pulses in granular media and their interaction with linear or nonlinear interfaces gives rise to a diversity of intriguing physical phenomena which have recently attracted great attention from the scientific community. Granular chains composed of a linear array of lightly pre-compressed elastic particles support the propagation of strongly nonlinear solitary waves with unique properties such as compact support and high tunability of wave speed [1]. These unique properties have recently been exploited for non-destructive testing (NDT) of materials and structures in a wide range of applications [2-7]. Several studies have shown that solitary waves in granular chains can be effectively used to measure elastic properties of materials and structures [2-3], such as beams and plates, while others have demonstrated the possibility of using granular chains for the detection of defects embedded in a structure [4-5], or the measurement of elastic-plastic properties of low density foams [7]. Although recent studies have shown that solitary waves in granular chains can be effectively used in various NDT applications involving elastic and isotropic test structures, only limited information is currently available in the literature on how solitary waves interact with structures made of composite materials whose mechanical properties are strongly anisotropic in nature. To fill existing gaps in the literature, we conduct, in this study, experiments and numerical calculations to examine the interaction between solitary waves in granular chains and transversely isotropic composite beams. Experiments are performed using a vertical array of 21 steel beads placed in direct contact with a simply-supported composite beam at mid-span. Single solitary waves are generated in the granular chain through impact of a striker bead, and the incident and reflected solitary waves are measured using a force sensor embedded in one of the particles. The obtained measurements are used to study the effect of lamina properties, composite layup, laminate thickness and width on the delays and amplitude ratios of the first two reflected solitary waves. The experimental evidence is also used to validate a previously developed numerical model based on discrete elements and classical beam theory.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation and mechanical testing

In this study, two types of composite laminates are considered, carbon-fibre/epoxy and glass-fibre/epoxy composites; these are referred to here, as CFRP and GFRP, respectively. For the sake of brevity, only the fabrication of the CFRP samples is detailed in the following. The fabrication of the GFRP laminates follows a similar route.

The CFRP laminates were fabricated using an out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepreg material (CYCOM 5320-1, Cytec Industries Inc.) with woven fibre architecture based on an eight harness satin weave design. The prepreg had a thickness of 0.65 mm and a weight fraction of fibres of 0.64. The laminate was manufactured using a hot pressing method from five plies of 250 x 250 mm prepreg with a stacking sequence of $[\pm 0^\circ]_5$. The prepreg stack was then positioned between the platens of a hot-press and compacted for six hours under a constant pressure and temperature of 500 kPa and 177°C, respectively. The press was then rapidly cooled to a temperature below 50°C, and the laminate was removed from the press. After the fabrication process was completed, the laminate was cut into rectangular coupons of length L_s and width B by using a diamond saw. Following the fabrication of the five ply laminate, CFRP laminates with three and nine plies were also manufactured by the same method as described above. The final laminate thicknesses H were 1.05 mm, 1.75 mm and 3.15 mm for composites with three, five and nine plies respectively.

To measure the flexural properties of the fabricated composite laminates, three-point bending tests were performed using an Instron 4505 UTM with a 50 kN load cell. The test specimens were prepared as follows. As detailed in Section 2.1, a total of six laminates were fabricated, three CFRP laminates with thicknesses of 1.05 mm, 1.75 mm and 3.15 mm, respectively, and three GFRP laminates with thicknesses 1.0 mm, 2.0 mm and 3.0 mm, respectively; for each laminate, test coupons of length $L_s = 70$ mm and width $B = 20$ mm were cut in the 0° - and 45° -direction of the laminate. The CFRP and GFRP specimens cut in the 0° -direction are designated here as CFRP/ 0° and GFRP/ 0° , respectively, while those cut in the 45° -direction are referred to as CFRP/ 45° and GFRP/ 45° , respectively, as shown in Table 1. In the bending tests, a single test coupon was placed on two cylindrical steel rollers (diameter 10 mm, length 40 mm) separated by a span of $L = 60$ mm. The load was applied at mid-span through a steel roller (diameter 10 mm, length 40 mm) which was displaced at a rate of 1.0 mm/min until ultimate failure occurred. The measured load-deflection response was used to determine the flexural strength σ_{fu} and modulus E_f of each laminate (see Table 1). Since the measured flexural modulus E_f of the GFRP and CFRP laminates were not very sensitive to the laminate thickness, we included in Table 1 only the values measured for laminates with thickness 1.75 mm in case of CFRP, or 2.0 mm in case of GFRP.

Specimen designation	Fibre direction	Average density ρ (kg m ⁻³)	Thicknesses H (mm)	Flexural strength σ_{fu} (MPa)	Young's modulus E_f (GPa)
CFRP/ 0°	$0^\circ, 90^\circ$	1450	1.05/1.75/3.15	862	63.0
CFRP/ 45°	$45^\circ, -45^\circ$	1450	1.05/1.75/3.15	404	18.3
GFRP/ 0°	$0^\circ, 90^\circ$	1780	1.0/2.0/3.0	463	18.9
GFRP/ 45°	$45^\circ, -45^\circ$	1780	1.0/2.0/3.0	365	14.1

Table 1 Average density, thickness and flexural properties of the tested laminates

2.2 Non-destructive testing using solitary waves

To study experimentally the interaction between solitary waves in granular chains and adjacent composite laminates, we assembled a granular chain composed of 21 identical spherical steel particles (radius $R = 9.5$ mm, mass $m = 28.2$ g) made of hardened AISI 52100 steel with density $\rho_s = 7860$ kg·m⁻³, Young's modulus $E = 208$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ and yield strength $\sigma_Y \approx 1600$ MPa. As shown in Fig. 1a, the granular chain was vertically aligned using four polished stainless steel rods

which were fitted into two aluminium plates and bolted to an aluminium frame using L-shaped clamps (see Fig. 1a). As shown in Fig. 1b, the last chain particle was in direct contact with a laminated composite beam (span L , thickness H , width B) supported by two cylindrical steel rollers (4 mm diameter) at the bottom face. The specimens were cut from the laminates described in Section 2.2 and their properties are listed in Table 1.

Single solitary waves were generated in the granular chain by dropping the first bead (also referred to as the striker bead) onto the rest of the chain from a drop height of $h = 40$ mm (see Fig. 1b). This choice of drop height was sufficiently low to avoid damage and failure in the composite specimen and to avoid excessive dissipation by plastic deformation in the chain particles. The incident and reflected nonlinear waves were measured using a piezoelectric disc element embedded in particle 11 (counted from the top of the chain). This sensor bead generates voltage proportional to the applied compressive force, and was fabricated, assembled and calibrated using the same approach as described in [2]. The output signal from the sensor bead was displayed and stored using an oscilloscope (Keysight DSOX2014A) and the obtained data was sent to a computer for further processing. For each specimen, five repeated tests were performed to determine the scatter in the measurements and to assess the reliability of our experimental apparatus.

Figure 1: Photograph (a) and schematic illustration (b) of the experimental setup

3 NUMERICAL MODELLING

The discrete element model developed by Schiffer and Kim [3] was used to study the formation of reflected solitary waves at the chain-sample interface, and to compare with the measurements. In this Section, a brief outline of this model is given; for a more detailed description, the reader is referred to [3].

Following Schiffer and Kim [3], we treat the wave propagation problem as one-dimensional and model the granular chain as an array of $N = 21$ point masses connected through nonlinear spring-dashpot systems whose response is described by the constitutive equation

$$F_i = \begin{cases} A\delta_i^{3/2} + \gamma\dot{\delta}_i & \text{for } \delta_i \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } \delta_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the index i denotes the particle number counted from the top of the chain ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$), $\delta_i = u_i - u_{i+1}$, represents the chain compression between particles i and $i+1$, over-dots are derivatives with respect to time, γ denotes the chain dissipation coefficient and A is a measure of the stiffness of the Hertzian contact and is given by

$$A = \frac{E\sqrt{2R}}{3(1-\nu^2)} \quad (2)$$

where E , ν and R are Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and radius of a chain particle, respectively. Assuming that the response of the laminate is linear elastic and that contact deformations between the last chain particle and the laminate are vanishingly small and dissipation-free, the governing equations for the discrete particle model can be written as

$$m\ddot{u}_1 + F_1 - mg = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$m\ddot{u}_i + F_i - F_{i-1} - mg = 0 \quad (i = 2, 3, \dots, N-1), \quad (4)$$

$$\left(m + \frac{1}{2}L\mu\right)\ddot{u}_N + \frac{\pi^4 E_f B H^3}{24L^3} u_N - F_{N-1} - mg = 0, \quad (5)$$

where $g = 9.81 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$ is the gravitational acceleration in the vertical chain, m is the mass of a chain particle, E_f is the flexural modulus of the laminate (see Table 1), B and H are the laminate's width and thickness, and F_i is the contact force between particles i and $i+1$, as defined in eq.(1).

To initiate the propagation of the incident solitary wave, an initial velocity of $v_0 = (2gh)^{1/2} = 0.88 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ is assigned to the striker bead. Furthermore, initial displacements were assigned to all chain particles to include the effect of gravity on the chain compression. According to [3], these displacements are given by

$$\tilde{u}_i = \tilde{u}_N + \left[\frac{mg(N-i)}{A}\right]^{2/3}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{u}_N = \frac{24L^3 mgN}{\pi^4 E_f B H^3} \quad (7)$$

represents the initial deflection of the beam. With the initial conditions given above, the system response was calculated by integrating eqs. (3)-(5) numerically using the Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg method in MATLAB. The predicted particle displacements $u_i(t)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) were substituted into eq.(1) to obtain the contact forces in the chain, $F_i(t)$ ($i = 1, \dots, N-1$), from which the force measured by the sensor particle was calculated via

$$F_{sens}(t) = \frac{F_{10}(t) + F_{11}(t)}{2}. \quad (8)$$

The predicted sensor force vs. time histories (eq. (8)) were used to determine the delay and amplitude of the reflected solitary waves, as in the experimental investigation.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this Section, we present the measurements obtained with our solitary wave-based test apparatus and compare the experimental results to predictions obtained from the numerical model described in Section 3.

4.1 Sensing of directional stiffness

To probe the ability of our solitary wave based technique to measure directional changes in the stiffness of a composite laminate, we present, in Fig. 2a, measurements and DE predictions of sensor force vs. time histories obtained from tests performed on CFRP/0° and CFRP/45° laminates with thickness $H = 1.8 \text{ mm}$ (see Table 1). The span and width of both specimens was $L = 60 \text{ mm}$ and $B = 20 \text{ mm}$, respectively, and $t = 0$ corresponds to the time of impact of the striker bead on the chain. Note

that the results for the CFRP/45° beam are vertically shifted by 500 N, for illustration purposes. For both beams, the arrival of the incident solitary wave at the sensor bead is recorded at time $t = 0.28$ ms, showing a symmetric pulse of amplitude ≈ 450 N. For the CFRP/0° beam, two distinct reflected solitary waves are observed, one at $t = 2.2$ ms, representing the primary reflected solitary wave (PRW), and a second one at $t = 2.7$ ms, also denoted as the secondary reflected solitary wave (SRW). To characterize the delay in the formation of a reflected solitary wave, we define as the delay the time difference between the arrival time of the incident wave at the sensor bead and the arrival time of the PRW at the same location. With this mind, the PRW and SRW delays for the CFRP/0° beam are evaluated as $T_{\text{PRW}} = 1.92$ ms and $T_{\text{SRW}} = 2.42$ ms, respectively. On the other hand, the PRW and SRW delays associated with the response of the CFRP/45° beam are considerably longer than those of the CFRP/0° beam, reporting $T_{\text{PRW}} = 2.92$ ms and $T_{\text{SRW}} = 3.82$ ms, respectively. The increased delay in the formation of reflected solitary waves can be attributed to the fact that the CFRP laminate is strongly anisotropic and has a much lower flexural modulus in the 45°-direction compared to the 0°-direction (see Table 1). Consequently, the CFRP/45° beam responds to loading by the incident solitary wave with larger mid-span deflection and possesses a longer response time compared to the CFRP/0° beam, as seen from the DE predictions in Fig. 2b. The prolonged response time of the CFRP/45° causes a delay in the formation of the PRW and SRW which is triggered by a collision between the elastically rebounding beam and the rest of the chain (see Fig. 2b). Furthermore, we note that the DE predictions are found in good agreement with the measurements (see Fig. 2a), suggesting that the formulation of the DE model is adequate for the problem investigated here. However, it should be mentioned that the DEM consistently over-predicts the PRW and SRW amplitudes due to its inability to describe accurately the dynamics at the beam-chain interface. This was also noted in a previous study [3] to which the reader is referred for further information.

It is evident from Fig. 2 that the measured PRW and SRW delays are highly sensitive to the layup of the composite, suggesting that the developed diagnostic scheme, based on solitary waves, is capable of detecting anisotropy in the elastic stiffness of engineering composites. In the following, we examine the effects of geometrical parameters, such as beam thickness and width, on the characteristic features of the reflected solitary waves for both GFRP and CFRP composites.

Figure 2: Predicted and measured time histories of sensor force (a) and beam displacement (b) for CFRP laminates cut in two different directions; the samples dimensions are $H = 1.8$ mm, $L = 60$ mm and $B = 20$ mm; the results shown in (a) are shifted vertically for illustration purposes.

4.1 Sensing of laminate thickness

We proceed to examine the effects of laminate thickness on the characteristic features of the reflected solitary waves for both CFRP and GFRP beams. In addition to the PRW and SRW delays defined in Section 4.1, we introduce two additional parameters, referred here to as the amplitude ratios

$$AR_{PRW} = \frac{A_{PRW}}{A_{IN}}, \quad AR_{SRW} = \frac{A_{SRW}}{A_{IN}}, \quad (9)$$

to quantify the relative intensity of the PRW and SRW, respectively. Here, A_{IN} , A_{PRW} and A_{SRW} are the sensor force amplitudes of the incident, primary reflected and secondary reflected solitary waves, respectively.

In Fig. 3a, the measured PRW and SRW delays are plotted as functions of the laminate thickness H for the case of CFRP/0° beams (see Table 1) of width $B = 20$ mm; we also include, for comparison, the corresponding predictions obtained from the DEM (solid lines). Note that the measurements were highly repeatable and therefore, the error bars (representing one standard deviation of repeated measurements) are not clearly visible in Fig. 3a. The measurements show that the delays of both the PRW and SRW decrease significantly with increasing beam thickness H , and the DE predictions confirm this. For the thickness range considered here, the DE predictions are found in very good agreement with the measurements, suggesting that our DEM is able to correctly predict the PRW and SRW delays associated with the response of the laminated composites.

In Fig. 3b, we present the corresponding DE predictions and measurements of the amplitude ratios AR_{PRW} and AR_{SRW} , respectively. For the range considered here, the measured amplitude ratios of the PRWs are higher than those of the SRWs, as expected. The DE predictions confirm this trend and are found in good agreement with the measurements.

Figure 3: Predictions and measurements of delay (a) and amplitude ratio (b) of primary and secondary reflected solitary waves for CFRP/0° laminates of width $B = 20$ mm as functions of H .

Similar information is provided in Fig. 4 for beams made of GFRP/0°. Since the flexural stiffness of the GFRP/0° is significantly smaller than that of the CFRP/0° (see Table 1), the PRW and SRW delays associated with the GFRP/0° (Fig. 4a) are generally longer than those of the CFRP/0° (Fig. 3b). Again, the PRW and SRW measurements are found in good agreement with the corresponding DE predictions. On the other hand, larger discrepancies are observed between predicted and measured AR_{PRW} values (see Fig. 4b), which can be attributed to the fact that the DE model does not account for contact deformations at the chain-beam interface which provide ‘damping’ to the reflected waves.

Figure 4: Predictions and measurements of delay (a) and amplitude ratio (b) of primary and secondary reflected solitary waves for GFRP/0° laminates of width $B = 20$ mm as functions of H .

4.3 Effect of beam width

To examine the effect of beam width on the delays and amplitude ratios of the PRW and SRW, we tested three CFRP/0° specimens of width $B = 10, 30$ and 45 mm, respectively, with constant thickness $H = 1.8$ mm and span $L = 60$ mm. The PRW and SRW delays obtained from these tests are plotted against the beam width in Fig. 5a along with the DE predictions. The data show decreasing PRW and SRW delays with increasing beam width, which can be explained by increased beam inertia that retards the dynamic deformation of the beam and decreases the duration of the interaction period. The DE predictions are found in good agreement with the measurements in Fig. 5a. However, DE predictions become less accurate with increasing values of B , as a consequence of increased transverse bending deformations which are not accounted for in the DEM.

Figure 5: Predictions and measurements of delay (a) and amplitude ratio (b) of primary and secondary reflected solitary waves for CFRP/0° laminates of thickness $H = 1.8$ mm as functions of B .

In Fig. 5b we present the corresponding measurements and DE predictions of the amplitude ratios associated with the PRW and SRW. Similar to what presented in Fig. 4b, the DE model over-predicts the measured AR_{PRW} values, while good agreement between predictions and measurements is reported for AR_{SRW} .

5 CONCLUSIONS

We studied the interaction of solitary waves in a granular chain with composite beams using experimental and numerical approaches. Experiments were conducted using a setup in which a vertically aligned array of steel beads contacts a simply-supported composite laminate at mid-span. A striker bead is dropped from a given height to initiate the propagation of a solitary wave in the granular chain whose interaction with the composite beam gives rise to the propagation of multiple reflected solitary waves in the chain. The delay and amplitude of these reflected solitary waves were measured and used to validate successfully a previously developed numerical model based on discrete elements and classical beam theory.

It was found that the delay and amplitude ratios of the reflected solitary waves are highly sensitive to the lamina properties, composite layup and thickness of the tested laminate. This allows concluding that the developed apparatus, based on solitary waves, is capable of measuring directional stiffness variations in engineering composites, offering a low-cost and time-efficient alternative to conventional destructive test methods.

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